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**Arid Horticulture for Enhancing Productivity and
Economic Empowerment**

Underutilized arid vegetables for income

Dryland horticulture has enormous scope in providing nutrition rich food, social security and eco-restoration to the inhabitants of desert and tribal areas. While assessing distinctness of hot arid and semi-arid agroclimate of Rajasthan, it is accomplished that non-availability of apposite crop-genotypes and production techniques are two prime limitations in success of vegetable culture. Traditionally, kachri (*Cucumis melo* var. *callosus* / *agrestis*), kakadia / snap melon (*Cucumis melo* var. *momordica*), mateera (*Citrullus lanatus*), tinda (*Praecitrullus fistulosus*) and guar (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) are grown. Besides, khejri (*Prosopis cineraria*) is playing a vital role in long-established farming, and its tender pods are used for vegetable purpose. With the establishment of national centre in 1993 at Bikaner, systematic research was started for germplasm conservation and utilization in native crop-plants having vegetable potentialities. The crop-genotype studies over 45 vegetables at Central Institute of Arid Horticulture, demonstrated that there is a breathtaking scope in getting quality marketable yield adopting production site management concept (HBCPSMA), provided trait specific genotypes. With khejri models, higher yield in prioritized vegetable and income @ ₹75,000–2,25,000 ha/year was obtained in comparison to the traditional cropping (₹23,000–42,000). Thus, technological advancement in under-scored arid vegetables is a boon towards better income and nutrition in resource constrained environment.

Vegetable production with under-scored/native crop-plant is pre-dominantly found to be most appropriate and stable. At present, exploitation of under-scored crops and native tree-plants of vegetable significance is negligible, unorganized and productivity and quality of produce is marginal. This is primarily because of unavailability of desirable crop-genotypes suited to prevailing climatic situations and/or environmentally stressed production sites, unavailability of quality seed / planting material of the recommended crop-genotypes and lack of apposite techniques. Therefore, there are essentially two complementary requirements i.e. improvement in genetic make-up as provisions for desirable crop-genotypes and creation of favourable micro-climate at production site of targeted zone to minimize the ill-effects of adversity.

UNDERUTILIZED ARID VEGETABLES

In the vast spread arid farm-lands, cultivation of pearl millet,

cluster bean, moth bean, sesame, kachri, snap melon, mateera, tinda and tumba is done as component crops between natural plantations of khejri, besides native crop-plants (jharber, bordi, lasora, pilu, ker, kumat, phog, khimp, sewan, etc.) forming traditional farming systems. With

Drip technology in cucurbit cultivation

Bottle gourd variability in tribal areas

Drought tolerant mateera Thar Manak

changed scenario, now, focus is shifted from sustenance to remunerative but mono-cropping is risky for dry-land horticulture. Therefore, the traditional systems predominantly mixed cropping needs multi-dimensional interventions through prioritized crops and newer technological advancement, and now, it can be exploited with most prospective species, i. e. khejri adopting horticulture based crop production site management approach (HBCPSMA).

Owing to some extent manageable agro-climatic conditions, availability of limited irrigation facilities and varying production systems (rainfed or irrigated), a careful selection of crop-genotypes and combinations for the specified sub-zone could be a boon for success in arid vegetable culture. The peculiar conditions impart unique quality in kachri, kakadia, mateera, tinda, kakri, ivy gourd, spiny gourd, bottle gourd, muskmelon, chilli, cluster bean, beans and sehjan. An enormous scope to promote large-scale seed production in cucurbits, brinjal, tomato, chilli, okra, early cauliflower, pea, cowpea, cluster bean, Indian bean, sword bean, velvet bean, palak, methi, and truck gardening for the distance market in particular to the cole crops, onion, carrot, melons and chillies do exist with irrigated farm-land. The indigenous value added products from khejri, ker, kachri, phog and sehjan can be exploited, and dehydrated products have lot of market potential (like *Panchkutta*) as concentrated vegetable. The

condition of high temperature and low humidity helps in solar drying of number of vegetables, and this practice is already common for drying of pods of khejri (*sangri*) and cluster bean (*guar-phali*), fruits of kachri, kakadia (*kheleera*), tinda (*phophalia*), ker and lasora, and leaves of methi, sehjan and curry-leaf.

Better Genotypes

Despite a large number of varietal progress in vegetables under national network, very few crop-genotypes are performing well with varying environment. However, much work on developing varieties and value-added genotype is needed for under-utilized native crop-plants of regional significance, and also on un-exploited adaptive vegetables for cultivation with arid to semi-arid agro-climate.

Conservation germplasm: The land-races and local cultivars are source of genes for stress tolerance, adaptability, quality and therefore, their collection and evaluation is the pre-requisite for potential utilization of genetic resources. At Bikaner, systematic research was started from 1994 and over two decade period, several crop-specific and multi-crop explorations were made for survey and collection of vegetable germplasm from parts of arid, semi-arid and tribal areas of Rajasthan and Gujarat. As a result, 1725 accessions were collected and evaluated in vegetables at the institute and out of them 1060

Drought tolerant bottle gourd (Thar Samridhi)

Genetic variability in snap melon

Snap melon AHS-82 in bearing

germplasm were deposited at NBPGR for conservation. Based on characterization over period (1994–2016), potential crop-germplasm were identified and developed lines from base material are maintained (500), and it consists of kachri (68), snap melon (65), kakri (18), muskmelon (60), mateera (65), round melon (10), gourds (65), beans (40), khejri (15) and others under-utilized including perennial vegetables.

Utilization of vegetable germplasm: To promote profitable vegetable culture under arid agro-climate, systematic crop improvement project was formulated and started from 1994, and the prime emphasis was on drought hardy under-utilized crops such as kachri, snap melon, kakri, mateera, tinda and guar. Mission mode action is taken for khejri and heat tolerant breeding in melons, gourds and brinjal. This resulted in development of high yielding and quality producing genotypes of mateera (AHW-19, AHW-65 and Thar Manak), kachri (AHK-119 and AHK-200), snap melon (AHS-10 and AHS-82), kakri (AHC-2, AHC-13 and Thar Sheetal), bottle gourd (Thar Samridhi), cluster bean (Thar Bhadavi), Indian bean (Thar Kartiki and Thar Maghi), sword bean (Thar Mahi), khejri (Thar Shobha) and brinjal (Thar Rachit) and these are recommended for cultivation. The promising lines of bottle gourd (AHL-24), ridge gourd (AHRG-1 and AHRG-8), sponge gourd (AHSG-4 and AHSG-5), round melon (AHRM-1 and AHRM-2), muskmelon (CIAH-1), chilli

Khejri-based kachri cultivation

Vegetable type cluster bean (Thar Bhadavi) for rainfed cultivation

(HRM-1), brinjal (CIAH-22), ivy gourd (AHIG-1), palak (AHL-1) and moringa (AHMO-1-4s) were used in breeding and material is under testing.

In addition, some new breeding material is also developed for their trait specific studies under high temperature and abiotic stressed arid environment, and it consists of kachri (AHK-411, AHK-564 and AHK-572), snap melon (DKS/AHS-2011/2), mateera (AHW RSS-1 and AHW BSM-1), ridge gourd (AHRG-15-4-1), sponge gourd (AHSG/2015/F₅/1), bottle gourd (AHL-1 Oblong-1 and AHL-1 Long/2015/F₆/1), bitter melon (AHBT-2), tomato (AHL-1 and AHL-2), cowpea (AHCP-1-1), Indian bean (KSB-66), cluster bean (AHG-20), velvet bean (AHVB-1), methi (AHL-1), bathua (AHL-1), carrot (AHDC-1) and khejri (CIAH Selection-2).

Production Technology

To standardize production techniques and good management practices for the vegetable culture in sandy soils of hot arid agro-climate, series of crop-specific

Sword bean Thar Mahi

Stresses tolerant brinjal Thar Rachit

and combination experimental trials were conducted with check-bed, channel, drip and sprinkler method under rainfed or limited irrigation from 1997-2016. The prioritized vegetables such as kachri, snap melon, kakri, tinda, mateera, gourds, brinjal, cluster bean, beans, palak, sehjan and khejri were studied for developing packages of practices.

Development of khejri based crop production sites:

Khejri is a versatile tree of Thar desert and is most potential perennial component compatible to almost all companion crop-plant in farming system of north-western part of India. The budded khejri plant grows luxuriantly under the extreme hot and dry conditions. This eco-restoring tree is not only helping in fertility build-up but also minimizing the ill-effects from higher solar radiation, temperature and hot wind. Systematic khejri (Thar Shobha) plantations either high-density or paired-rows at wider-spacing exhibited significant effects in creating favourable micro-climate at the developed production site and helping in promotion of pollinating agents.

Based on the region specific long-term crop research findings under HBCPSMA concept (1994 to 2016) some principles/recommendations are suggested for development and management of khejri based production sites. Production sites should be developed in accordance to topography of sand-dune farm-land and soil conditions. Fencing of production site and development of multi-tier rows of seedling plantation with desert trees (khejri, lasora, rohida, bordi, ker, kumat) and shrubs (jharber, phog) all-around the field block is prime consideration for creating favourable micro-climate and it is essential to protect the crops from extremes of hot, cold and wind conditions, and wild animals. Four-side area of production site is developed as multi-tier rows of seedling plantation (single / paired, 4m x 4m) with directions for khejri and lasora or rohida, kumat (south), khejri and lasora or ker, rohida (west), khejri and kumat or rohida, bordi

Trellis technology for vertical harvesting

(north) and khejri and ker or rohida (east).

The innovative techniques / practices under HBCPSMA includes selection and development of khejri planting model, and preparation, maintenance and management for crops under cultivation based on available resources at production site. Adoption of pre-monsoon deep ploughing in June prior to crop-sowing, and post-monsoon ploughing after crop-harvest in November month as technique resulted into more *in-situ* rain-water harvesting, soil moisture conservation and weed-free fields. Keeping crop-field fallow for 1-2 months either in April-June or October-November, is an essential practice for soil-health security and fertility build-up. Besides, seed/plant selection, sowing / planting techniques, maintenance of crop-plant population and prophylactic protective measures are management practices essentially required for improving yield and productivity of the resources, and all-these together only worthy when the best suited genotype is chosen for vegetable cultivation.

On the basis of crop potentialities, so far, three horticultural combinations are recommended for developing khejri based production sites. The first two are primarily with rainfed or limited irrigation, and namely are organic *Panchkuta* production technology (khejri, ker, lasora, kumat and kachri) and native crop production technology (khejri + native vegetables) in which khejri planting model KM-1 (4 m x 4 m) or KM-3 (8 m x 8 m) is practiced, respectively with hectare block lay-out. For prioritized vegetable crop sequence and irrigated culture, wide-spacing planting model (KM-9 or KM-11) is most appropriate and here paired khejri rows (4 m x 4 m) are developed at 24 m or 44 m distances, respectively with four hectare block lay-out and it is intensive crop production technology. For systematic block planting, single or paired rows of khejri var. Thar Shobha should be lay-out in the east-west direction and wider area is the developed fields for crop cultivation.

Khejri var. Thar Shobha plantation exhibited good canopy at 6th year-age and here annual June pruning is adopted and tender pod (7.22) and loong (8.15) yield (kg/plant) was harvested. With khejri based production sites, tender pod yield of 31.84, 5.84, 12.12 and 7.58 q/ha was recorded under KM-1, KM-3, KM-9 and

High quality seed production in native cucurbits (kakadia)

Dehydration in snap melon fruits

KM-11 planting model, respectively. Similarly, marketable fruit yield of kachri var. AHK-119 (42.48-88.56 q/ha) and tender pod yield of cluster bean var. Thar Bhadavi (45.32-85.45 q/ha) was obtained with the varying production situations from 2014-15 to 2016-17. Thus, this concept offers incredible scope for vegetable combinations with khejri models for the highest returns.

Agro-techniques for arid vegetables: The systematic experimentation on native, under-scored and un-exploited vegetables adopting channel or drip system

of crop production in sandy soils resulted in standardization of agro-techniques at CIAH and is most practicable for cucurbits, beans and brinjal. Channel and drip technology is input saving as water (30-50%), fertilizers (30-35%) and labour (25-30%), besides, it is easy in management. For normal sowing, onset of rains in July and February is the best for rainy-winter and spring-summer crop, respectively. The channel or surface covering protective tent-technology developed for cucurbits sowing during the first week of January is also highly remunerative for early yields, and it is very simple, low-cost and excellent mechanism to escape from severe winter situations under hot arid agro-climate.

Surface and tent covering technology

Indian bean Thar Kartiki

After selecting proper field-plot, marked area should be cross-ploughed 2-3 times followed by planking, and it should be started prior to 10-15 days of sowing. About 50-60 cm wide and 20-25 cm deep channels (furrows) are made at 2.0 m distances for kachri, snap melon, kakri, tinda, mateera and gourds, and also with trellis system of Indian bean, sword bean, velvet bean, spiny gourd, ivy gourd and bitter gourd cultivation. For solanaceous crops, channels are made in continuous manner or laterals at 1.0 m distances.

For uniform water distribution, crop-sown channels should be 25 m in length on one-side of delivery-line, and 50 × 50 m plot size is appropriate. Similarly, one-side length of laterals should not exceed 25 m and unit plot size should be of 50 m × 50 m with control valves, and 4 ha vegetable block can be managed with a drip system unit having diggi based PVC pipe-line network of main (110 mm), sub-main (75 mm) and plot-line (63 mm) for pressurized irrigation.

On the basis of soil fertility, building-up studies at 3, 6 and 9 years of vegetable cultivation, it is established that only channels as seed-bed needs to be fertilized and mixed thoroughly, and basal dose of FYM (50 q), vermin-compost (5 q), DAP (100 kg), SSP (100 kg), urea (50 kg), MOP (50 kg) and 10 kg neem-leaf powder per hectare is enough for maintaining productivity. For drip technology, here, after fertilization channels are converted into seed-beds on

which laterals are laid-down. Cucurbits seeds are sown at 50 cm distances and sowing should be done only at inner down-side of northern slope of channels or near to the drippers of lateral lines.

About 1-2 kg seed is enough for one hectare for most of arid cucurbits and 10-15 kg for beans. Prior to sowing, seed should be soaked in water for 2-6 hours and also treated with fungicide. At each sowing point, 2-3 seeds are sown. After good germination and when seedling attains 8-10 cm height or is 18-21 days age-old, thinning should be done keeping one or two healthy plants at each point.

The crop should be irrigated at intervals of 5-6 days by flood method only in the channels or at 2-3 days for 1.5-2.0 hours with drip technology (laterals 14-16 mm and 4 lph in-line emitters) under sandy soils. Manual hoeing and weeding in channels / seed-bed is done at 18-21, 30-35 and 45-55 days after sowing. Similar schedule is recommended for application of urea (50 kg/ha) in 2-3 split doses as early plant growth, flowering and fruit setting stages and spraying of insecticides to manage insects.

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